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Does the initial distribution of EU ETS allowances affect the production levels of French companies?

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This article analyses the relationship between the initial allocation of allowances under the European Union Emissions Trading Scheme (EU ETS) and production levels in the French manufacturing sector. To this end, we have created an original panel database comprising 376 firm-year observations from 2007 to 2018. This database links firms' financial characteristics to EU ETS data provided by the EU Transaction Log. Using a Translog function, we demonstrate that firms' production levels depend on the initial distribution of allowances. Heterogeneity analysis corroborates the main results for companies that received the fewest allowances and for those in a purchasing position. The main result is also applicable to companies operating on the domestic market and to those in the food, minerals and metallurgy sectors. Therefore, this study challenges Montgomery's (1972) findings, despite the fact that the initial distribution of quotas is exogenous and the ETS appears to operate competitively. Our results suggest that companies do not engage in static arbitrage, which calls into question the effectiveness of the ETS in achieving emission reductions at the lowest cost.

Keywords:

Translog production function; panel data; ETS; initial distribution; carbon quotas.

JEL Codes:

C33, G32, Q58, Q53, D22

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1 Introduction

Since the introduction of the Acid Rain program in the United States, decision-makers have increasingly turned to pollution quota markets as a means of internalising negative externalities. Prominent examples include the Regional Greenhouse Gas Initiative in the United States and the European Union Emissions Trading Scheme (EU ETS). Launched in 2005 by the Quotas Directive, the EU ETS applies to over 11,000 stationary installations and covers almost 45% of the European Union's greenhouse gas emissions. Initially established to assist in meeting the European Union's obligations under the Kyoto Protocol (European Commission, 2003), the EU ETS was subsequently made permanent. The carbon market is a vital part of the EU's policy to combat global warming and achieve the goals of the European Green Deal. The latter aims to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050 and calls for a reduction in net emissions of at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels.

The pioneering work of Crocker (1966) and Dales (1968) laid the foundations for the concept of a pollution quota market. These principles define the optimal pollution level, which is then used to allocate quotas to polluting agents. In the primary market, public authorities distribute these quotas to industries that are covered by the scheme. These industries can then transfer their quotas to a secondary market. This exchange provides incentives to reduce pollution at a lower cost (Montgomery, 1972). This makes quota markets more attractive than environmental standards, especially when there is asymmetric information about emission reduction costs.

Tradeable quota markets offer another advantage. Montgomery (1972) demonstrates that firms' abatement decisions are unaffected by the initial distribution of allowances. This result is obtained within the simple framework of perfect competition and under the assumption of an initial lump-sum distribution of allowances. When these hypotheses hold, quota markets become highly attractive to public authorities, as they can distribute quotas according to their objectives, such as raising income, or their distributive goals, without affecting market efficiency.⁴

⁴ The challenges of initial quota distribution can be examined using alternative analytical frameworks. For instance, a fee-based distribution generates income, unlike a free distribution. This method can be employed to achieve a "double dividend" by reducing distortionary taxes in the economy (Goulder, 1995), or for redistributive

Public authorities can rely on several types of initial free-of-charge distribution of allowances (Schwartz, 2009). In theory, the regulator can use any distribution rule. However, economic literature identifies two main types of free initial distribution, depending on whether or not they affect firms' behaviour.

The most well-known way to distribute initial allocations is based on past emissions. In the literature, the advantages of grandfathering are widely recognised. Firstly, it eases the transition from a situation without environmental regulation to one in which polluting emissions incur a cost. This makes the quota market more acceptable to firms. Secondly, since firms cannot modify their historical emissions data, this type of distribution is a lump sum and is therefore exogenous to the firms. The regulator can also use firms' production capacity to set initial allowances, independent of current production levels. This benchmarking criterion can also be considered a lump-sum transfer. In short, the Montgomery result should apply to the distribution of allowances under grandfathering or the production capacity criterion. The final distribution of allowances, or the level of production chosen by the company, should not be dependent on the quantity of allowances initially received.

Another method of distributing initial allowances is to base them on current production levels or the current inputs used. In this case, the distributed quotas are considered to be production subsidies (Fischer et al., 2004). This should therefore modify firms' production choices, leading to inefficiencies in production even if firms behave competitively in the goods market.

In practice, regulators have used various criteria when distributing free allowances. The RECLAIM programme, which targeted NO_x emissions, distributed allowances according to firms' historical emissions. Installations that have closed continue to benefit from free allowances, whereas new entrants must purchase them on the market. The Acid Rain programme relied mainly on past emissions as a criterion. The EU ETS also relied on grandfathering in its first two phases. For Phases 3 and 4, however, the EU ETS switched to using the benchmark criterion. Under this system, free allowances are equal to a greenhouse

purposes. The initial distribution can be designed to address carbon leakage, as in the EU ETS, or be based on the principle of profit neutrality (Nicolai, 2019). Taking lobbies into account, auctions can reduce market manipulation compared with free distribution (Cramton and Kerr, 2002).

gas emissions benchmark defined for each product, multiplied by historical production levels. As mentioned above, benchmarking is also considered to be outside the control of the firm.

Theoretical economic literature has explored hypotheses that challenge Montgomery's result. This topic has been well documented (e.g. Schwartz, 2006; Hintermann, 2011). For instance, Hahn (1984) and Westskog (1996) studied the assumption of market power in a static framework, while Hagem and Westskog (1998) studied it in a dynamic framework. Sartzetakis (1994, 1997a, 1997b), Schwartz (2007) and Bueb and Schwartz (2009, 2011) have considered how the quota market could be manipulated to achieve strategic goals in the goods market. Stavins (1995) introduced the concept of transaction costs, while Montero (1998) considered the impact of uncertainty regarding trading conditions.

Unlike the extensive theoretical literature on the subject, few econometric studies have examined the impact of the initial distribution of allowances on firms' decisions. For example, Fowlie and Perloff (2013) studied whether firms' emissions depended on the initial distribution of allowances under the RECLAIM programme. Their econometric analysis corroborates Montgomery's result. Other studies have focused on the ETS. Using a sample of European firms, Abrell et al. (2011) demonstrate that final emissions in Phase 1 and the beginning of Phase 2 depend on the initial distribution of allowances. However, according to Zaklan (2023), there is no evidence to suggest a link between initial distribution and emissions in the energy sector between 2008 and 2017. Ellerman and Reguant (2008) examined the relationship between initial distribution and production decisions in the Spanish coal sector. They demonstrated that the initial distribution had no significant impact on production levels. However, they overlooked the financial characteristics of firms. As the study is limited to the year 2006, it does not allow conclusions to be drawn about firm behaviour in subsequent phases of the ETS. Combes Motel et al. (2023) examine the link between firms' financial structures and the ETS. The authors demonstrate that firms that receive more allowances accumulate more debt than unregulated firms. To our knowledge, no study has empirically tested the impact of the initial distribution of allowances on the production levels of French manufacturing firms covered by the ETS.

Our research question could raise the issue of double causality. This would occur if a firm's output at time t depended on the initial allocation of allowances, which, in turn, depended on

the level of output at time t . However, the initial free allocation in phases 1 and 2 of the ETS is based on the principle of grandfathering. In phases 3 and 4, a benchmarking criterion is introduced. According to the economic literature, these two methods of distributing initial quotas are independent of companies' decisions at the time in question (Meunier et al., 2014). Furthermore, no study has identified imperfectly competitive behaviour within the ETS. We therefore base our empirical strategy on these results and we estimate companies' production levels using a translog production function. We would expect the production level of firms covered by the EU ETS to be independent of the initial allowance distributions.

To test this hypothesis, we are creating an original database that links environmental information about firms to information about their production processes. Environmental information is extracted from the European Union Transaction Log (EUTL) and financial information is obtained from the DIANE database. This gives us a database of 392 French manufacturing firms subject to the ETS. The manufacturing sector is France's fourth-largest emitter of greenhouse gases (GHGs), accounting for 18% of national emissions in 2022 compared to 27% in the early 1990s (CITEPA, 2023). This raises the question of whether the environmental policy that has enabled this reduction has impacted firms' production.

Using a Translog production function and a panel data estimator, we demonstrate that firms' production levels increase with the initial distribution of quotas. Therefore, the initial distribution of quotas in the ETS is not neutral and affects the production decisions of manufacturing firms. Therefore, Montgomery's result is challenged in the context of the EU ETS, even though the initial distribution is exogenous to firms and the secondary market is competitive. We then conduct a heterogeneity analysis to identify cases in which neutrality could apply. We find that the initial distribution of allowances has no impact on the choice of firms that received the largest initial endowment, those with a surplus of quotas, or firms that are mainly exporters. Neutrality emerges in Phase 2 of the ETS, as opposed to Phase 3, affecting firms in the automotive and paper sectors. Contrary to Montgomery (1972), our results suggest that firms do not engage in static arbitrage to determine their optimal quantity of pollution and, therefore, quotas. The opportunity cost of the quota is not considered in firms' economic calculations. In short, our study challenges Montgomery's theoretical result and calls into question the economic efficiency of the EU ETS.

The article is structured as follows: Section 2 introduces the ETS and its initial allocation of allowances. Section 3 provides the database and descriptive statistics. Section 4 describes the empirical methodology, and Section 5 presents the results. Section 6 concludes the article.

2 EU ETS and initial allocation of allowances

This section outlines the scope of the ETS and the initial allocation of allowances across its four implementation phases.

Under the 1997 Kyoto Protocol, the European Union pledged to reduce its carbon dioxide emissions by 8% below 1990 levels between 2008 and 2012. To achieve this objective, it adopted Directive 2003/87/EC in 2003. This Quotas Directive defines the regulatory framework for the European carbon market. When the EU ETS was launched in 2005, it covered 27 EU countries, which were joined by Norway, Iceland and Liechtenstein in 2008 and Croatia in 2013 (European Commission, 2021). Initially, the carbon market covered around 11,500 installations, representing two billion tonnes of carbon dioxide (Ellerman and Buchner, 2007).⁵

The EU ETS is now in its fourth phase. The different phases mainly differ in terms of their coverage and the rules for the initial distribution of allowances. We analyse the link between the initial distribution of allowances and firms' production levels below. While the first two phases used the grandfathering criterion, the last two used benchmarking. According to the literature, both allocation mechanisms are exogenous to firms.

2.1 Phase 1 and Phase 2

During Phases 1 (2005–2008) and 2 (2008–2012), most allowances were provided free of charge to installations, while 5% of allowances could be auctioned in Phase 1 and 10% in Phase 2. Member States were responsible for defining their National Allocation Plans (NAPs), which

⁵ The EU ETS covers carbon dioxide emissions from the production of electricity and heat, as well as from energy-intensive industrial sectors such as oil refining, steel production, and the production of iron, aluminium, and other metals, cement, lime, glass, ceramics, pulp, paper, cardboard, acids, and organic bulk chemicals. It also covers commercial aviation within the European Economic Area. It also includes nitrous oxide (N₂O) from the production of nitric acid, adipic acid, glyoxal, and glyoxylic acid; and perfluorocarbons (PFCs) from aluminium production. These various greenhouse gases are converted into tonnes of carbon equivalent.

listed the free allowances granted to each firm. These allowances were distributed first at the sector level and then at the plant level (Hanoteau, 2014).

In Phase 1, allowances were initially allocated to sectors based on their emission reductions between 1990 and 2002, their potential for further reductions, and their projected emissions for the period 2001–2006. Allowances were then distributed to firms according to their emissions in 2000–2002 and their share of sector emissions. In Phase 2, allowances were allocated based on a combination of criteria, including historical emissions, an average reference, forecasts of emissions growth and reduction potential. Some countries used average emissions from 2002 to 2005, while others used the period from 1998 to 2001. The distribution within a sector at firm level was then carried out based on firms' past emissions, generally for the 2004–05 period. In Phases 1 and 2, a reserve of free allowances was created for new installations and capacity extensions.

2.2 Phase 3

The NAPs in Phases 1 and 2 differed markedly across participating countries. Therefore, the revised directive of 2009 (European Commission, 2009a) introduced new, harmonised rules for the distribution of allowances in Phase 3 (2013–2020). Auctioning became the main rule. However, the revised directive permits exemptions for free allowances to prevent carbon leakage. The intention is for 30% of allowances to be free of charge by 2023, compared to 80% in 2013, and to auction 100% of allowances by 2030. For installations not exposed to a significant risk of carbon leakage, the new rule for distributing free allowances introduces a benchmark using the following formula, which is composed of four terms:

$$\text{Free-of-charge allowances} = BM \times HAL \times CLEF \times CSCF \text{ ou } LRF$$

With:

BM: benchmark;

HAL: historical activity level;

CLEF: carbon leakage exposure factor;

CSCF: cross-sectoral correction factor;

LRF: linear reduction factor.

The first term (BM) corresponds to the benchmark value, the main new feature of Phase 3. This is based on the carbon intensity of the 10% most emission-efficient plants between 2007 and 2009 when producing a given EU product. These benchmarks are expressed in tonnes of carbon dioxide per tonne of product manufactured. There are 52 products in the EU. The second term corresponds to the historical activity level (HAL) for a given plant. This is the median production value for the period 2005–2008 or 2009–2010, whichever is higher. A production forecast factor is also taken into account. The third term, the Carbon Leakage Exposure Factor (CLEF), is determined by the European Directive for each year between 2013 and 2020. The objective was to reduce the allocation of free allowances for these installations to 30% of the benchmark in 2020, compared with 80% in 2013 (see **Finally, there is a provision for new installations, including capacity extensions to existing plants.** These installations will benefit from a reserve of free allowances. Investments involving significant capacity extensions are eligible for this reserve provided the following two conditions are met: (i) the threshold for a significant capacity change is set at 10% of the plant's installed capacity; and (ii) the activity level must differ significantly. Specifically, the higher activity level must result in an annual allowance of more than 50,000, representing at least 5% of the provisional annual total for the installation. The quantity of free-of-charge allowances granted to new entrants is obtained by multiplying the benchmark by the installation's capacity — or increase in capacity — and a capacity utilisation factor. A linear factor of 1.74% generally applies to new entrants, significant capacity changes and partial closures, except for installations undergoing a significant capacity reduction. This reserve is allocated according to the sequential service rule.

Table 1).

The Quota Directive (2003/87/EC, as amended) (European Commission, 2021) sets the maximum annual quantity of free allowances at less than 43% of the emission cap defined by the Commission (Article 10a(5)). If the total quantity of claims for free allowances submitted by participating states exceeds this limit in any given year, a Cross-Sectoral Correction Factor (CSCF) should be applied. This factor is applied uniformly to all installations eligible for free allocation, reducing free allocation in Europe to below 43% of the emission cap. Otherwise, the linear reduction factor (LRF) of 1.74% applies in Phase 3.

The combination of these four terms determines the allocation of free allowances to an installation. However, there are exceptions to this rule. Firstly, a list of sectors "exposed" to the risk of carbon leakage was issued in 2009 for Phase 3 and in 2019 for Phase 4. For installations in these sectors, the free-of-charge allocation benchmark remains at 100% for both phases. Secondly, firms that shut down production will no longer receive any allowances. In contrast, a firm that reduces its activity by less than 50% will continue to receive all its free-of-charge allowances.

Finally, there is a provision for new installations, including capacity extensions to existing plants. These installations will benefit from a reserve of free allowances. Investments involving significant capacity extensions are eligible for this reserve provided the following two conditions are met: (i) the threshold for a significant capacity change is set at 10% of the plant's installed capacity; and (ii) the activity level must differ significantly. Specifically, the higher activity level must result in an annual allowance of more than 50,000, representing at least 5% of the provisional annual total for the installation. The quantity of free-of-charge allowances granted to new entrants is obtained by multiplying the benchmark by the installation's capacity — or increase in capacity — and a capacity utilisation factor. A linear factor of 1.74% generally applies to new entrants, significant capacity changes and partial closures, except for installations undergoing a significant capacity reduction. This reserve is allocated according to the sequential service rule.

Table 1. *CLEF* value from 2013 to 2020 in the ETS

2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
0.80	0.73	0.66	0.59	0.51	0.44	0.37	0.30

Source: Directive 2009/29/EC

2.3 Phase 4

In 2018, the Quota Directive was amended by Directive (EU) 2018/410 (European Parliament, 2018), establishing the fourth phase of the EU ETS from 2021 to 2030. This final phase is divided into two sub-periods: 2021–2025 and 2026–2030. The main principles introduced in Phase 3 remain unchanged, particularly concerning the scope of installations covered by the ETS. The initial distribution rule remains based on the combination of the aforementioned four terms, although their definitions may change.

The benchmark levels have been updated twice, using data from 2016–17 and 2021–22. Additionally, free-of-charge allowances are now calculated based on average annual activity levels rather than the median.

The cross-sectoral correction factor (CSCF) for the period from 2021 to 2025 is set at 100%, since the total of provisional allocations in Europe does not exceed the 43% emission cap limit for each year. The Linear Reduction Factor (LRF) will be set at 2.2%, enabling the proportion of free allowances to be reduced further.

Throughout this fourth phase, exposed sectors will be assigned a carbon leakage risk exposure factor (CLEF) of 1. Non-exposed sectors will be assigned a CLEF of 0.3 from 2021 to 2026; 0.225 from 2027 to 2028; 0.150 from 2029 to 2030; and 0 from 2031 onwards. Heat supplied to district heating networks will benefit from a CLEF of 0.3 throughout the entire period (see Compared with Phase 3, the main changes relate to the allocation of allowances for new entrants and capacity increases. For new entrants, the activity level is now based on the full calendar year following the start of normal operations, rather than the first three months of activity after the start date. In Phase 4, the concept of significant capacity modification has been replaced by the "dynamic allocation" principle. Free-charge allowances are adjusted annually to account for production increases and decreases, based on a threshold overshoot of plus or minus 15% of an installation's activity level.

Table 2).

Compared with Phase 3, the main changes relate to the allocation of allowances for new entrants and capacity increases. For new entrants, the activity level is now based on the full calendar year following the start of normal operations, rather than the first three months of activity after the start date. In Phase 4, the concept of significant capacity modification has been replaced by the "dynamic allocation" principle. Free-charge allowances are adjusted annually to account for production increases and decreases, based on a threshold overshoot of plus or minus 15% of an installation's activity level.

Table 2. *CLEF* value from 2021 to 2030 in the ETS

[2021-2026]	2027	2028	2029	2030
0.3	0,225	0,150	0,075	0

Source: Directive (UE) 2018/410

3 Data

This article uses econometric analysis to assess Montgomery's theoretical result, i.e. whether the initial distribution of allowances affects the production level of French companies subject to the EU ETS. To this end, we created an original panel database comprising 376 firm-year observations from 2007 to 2018, linking firms' financial characteristics to EU ETS data. Information on the financial characteristics of French companies was obtained from the DIANE database. Data on free-of-charge allowances and allowances exchanged under the EU ETS are taken from the European Union Transaction Log (EUTL).

Since firms are difficult to identify, we adopt the approach of Jaraitè et al. (2013), matching each firm to a unique SIREN number. This makes it easier to identify production units and establish correspondences with the DIANE database. Our analysis focuses on firms in the French manufacturing sector (section C of the NACE nomenclature), covering sectors 10 to 37. The period under consideration is 2007–2018, encompassing the first three phases of the EU ETS.

We have excluded 16 firms from our sample that have benefited from a capacity extension. These additional allowances are linked to current production levels and could cause an endogeneity problem.⁶ Our sample comprises 376 French companies. The number of firms in each sector is shown in Table 3.

In addition to the number of allowances allocated to firms (*FreeAllowances*) and verified emissions (*Emissions*), which are both measured in tonnes of CO₂ equivalent, the database includes information on the financial characteristics of firms. The *Production* variable represents the firm's total annual production value. The *Wages* variable represents the wages and salaries used to measure the amount of labour integrated into a firm's production process. This includes salaries, bonuses, welfare benefits (e.g. holiday vouchers and meal vouchers), and other forms of compensation. The *Assets* variable represents shareholders' capital. This is the money invested by the firm's shareholders or owners. It is a measure of a firm's financial health and its ability to invest in new projects. *Net fixed assets* are a financial indicator

⁶ Table A- 2 lists the firms concerned.

measuring the value of a firm's fixed assets after the deduction of accumulated depreciation and impairment allowances. These assets are held by the company to support its long-term growth. They include buildings, equipment, patents, and investments in other firms.

We have added the variable *Net tangible fixed assets*, representing tangible assets such as buildings, equipment, machinery, vehicles and land, which are held by the firm for long-term use in its business operations.⁷ Fixed assets and property, as well as plant and equipment, are two critical variables for investors, financial analysts and lenders because they indicate the value of a firm's income-generating assets. These variables proxy the firm's ability to repay its long-term debts and, ultimately, its financial stability.

Table 4 displays the descriptive statistics for these different variables. Of the 376 firms in our sample, 165 operate in the domestic market, while 211 operate in the international market. These figures suggest that French firms are active in international markets. However, firms subject to the ETS have reached a certain thermal capacity threshold. It could be thought that this criterion leads to the selection of significant-sized firms, who would thus be the most likely to operate in an international market.

We also note that the average number of allowances allocated for free exceeds verified emissions. Overall, the firms in our sample received more allowances than they required. More precisely, when we calculated the difference between initial allocations and verified emissions, we found that 64 firms were in deficit in 2008, at the start of Phase 2. This figure had increased to 168 by the time Phase 3 began in 2013. Consequently, the number of firms benefiting from surplus allocations has decreased over time. We account for this in our analysis of the initial distribution of allowances to determine its impact on firms' production levels.

⁷ Property, plant and equipment therefore include all equipment owned by firms, with the exception of patents and investments.

Table 3. Number of firms by sector

NAF Code	Sector name	N
10	Food	77
11	Beverages	6
12	Tobacco products	2
13	Textiles	4
16	Wood and cork products	10
17	Paper	69
19	Coking and refining	6
20	Chemicals	59
21	Pharmaceutical industry	5
22	Rubber and plastic	9
23	Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products	69
24	Basic metal	26
26	Computer electronic optical	3
27	Electrical equipment	2
28	Machinery	3
29	Automotive	18
30	Other transport equipment	6
31	Furniture	2

Full official sector names can be found in Table A- 1. NAF is the French Classification of Activities that has the same structure as the General Industrial Classification of Economic Activities used in the European Communities.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics

	Average	Standard error	Nb of firms
<i>FreeAllowances</i> (tonnes eq CO2)	96227.44	457226.2	376
<i>Emissions</i> (tonnes eq CO2)	90107.94	452267.4	376
<i>Emissions</i> (€)	576275.5	3316144	376
<i>Wages</i> (€)	38379.59	121967.2	376
<i>Assets</i> (€)	128507.2	429294.5	376
<i>Net fixed assets</i> (€)	207467.8	799706.6	376
<i>Net tangible fixed assets</i> (€)	115978.3	371963.3	376
Domestic market	-	-	165
International market	-	-	211
Net purchase (2008)	-	-	64
Net purchase (2013)	-	-	168

4 Econometric analysis

We use a panel data estimator to estimate a production function and study the relationship between the initial allocation of allowances and firms' output. The relationship between inputs and output may be Cobb–Douglas. This functional form implies that factor substitution

elasticities are both constant and equal to one. However, we opted for the Translog function, which is more flexible (Christensen et al., 1973). The econometric model is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln Production_{it} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln FreeAllowances_{it} + \beta_2 \ln Wages_{it} + \beta_3 \ln Assets_{it} \\ &+ \beta_4 \ln Wages_{it}^2 + \beta_5 \ln Assets_{it}^2 + \beta_6 \ln Wages_{it} \times \ln Assets_{it} + X_{it} \\ &+ \eta_i + \mu_t + v_{it} \end{aligned}$$

The variable $Production_{it}$ is the production of firm i in year t . $FreeAllowances$ is our independent variable of interest, indicating the initial quantity of allowances received by the firm. The variable $Wages$ indicates the wages and salaries received by employees. It measures the labour available for the firm's productive activity. $Assets$ corresponds to the firm's total assets. The vector X_{it} includes financial control variables, namely fixed assets and net property, plant and equipment as reported in Table 4. Fixed effects η_i capture firm or sector characteristics that do not vary over time, such as the sector of activity or location. μ_t allows us to take into account firm characteristics that vary over time but affect all firms in the same year, such as the carbon price or the national macroeconomic environment. v_{it} is the idiosyncratic part of the error term that is independently and identically distributed.

5 Results

Our results remain robust when fixed effects are introduced. Whatever the specification, we obtain a positive coefficient for our variable of interest. Firms' output levels increase with free-of-charge allowances under the ETS. More precisely, a 1% increase in free-of-charge allowances leads to an increase in output of between 0.011% and 0.014%.

Table 5 displays the results of the effect of the level of free-of-charge allowance allocation on the production level of French firms. The results are presented according to different combinations of fixed effects. We use either firm- or sector-specific fixed effects. Similarly, we introduce either year- or phase-fixed effects. The first three columns present the results obtained with firm-fixed effects, while the last three columns present the results obtained with sector-fixed effects.

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Table 5. Effect of free-of-charge allowances on production levels
Dependent variable: $\ln Production$

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
$\ln FreeAllowances$	0.013**	0.011**	0.012**	0.016***	0.014***	0.014***
	(0.005)	(0.006)	(0.006)	(0.005)	(0.005)	(0.005)
$\ln Wages$	0.435***	0.440***	0.441***	0.655***	0.659***	0.657***
	(0.048)	(0.048)	(0.048)	(0.038)	(0.038)	(0.038)
$\ln Wages^2$	-0.008	-0.008	-0.008	-0.012	-0.012	-0.012
	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.009)	(0.009)	(0.009)
$\ln Assets$	-0.066	-0.058	-0.059	0.513***	0.530***	0.522***
	(0.174)	(0.175)	(0.175)	(0.154)	(0.154)	(0.154)
$\ln Assets^2$	0.029**	0.029**	0.029**	0.042***	0.042***	0.041***
	(0.012)	(0.012)	(0.012)	(0.011)	(0.011)	(0.011)
$\ln Wages \times \ln Assets$	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004	-0.008***	-0.008***	-0.008***
	(0.003)	(0.003)	(0.003)	(0.002)	(0.002)	(0.002)
Observations	3212	3212	3212	3212	3212	3212
Firm fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO
Year fixed effects	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO
Sector fixed effects	NO	NO	NO	YES	YES	YES
Phase Fixed effects	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES
Control variables	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Robust standard errors are in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Control variables: *Net fixed assets* and *Net tangible assets*

6 Heterogeneity analysis

We investigate whether our main result varies depending on the initial distribution of allowances, the phase of ETS implementation, the market in which the firm operates and the sector to which the firm belongs.

6.1 Free-of-charge allowances

Our main finding is that firms' production levels tend to increase with the initial distribution of allowances. However, this result may depend on the quantity of allowances received by the firm. To test this assumption, we divided our sample into quartiles of free-of-charge allowances. The first quartile contains firms with the lowest allocations, and the last quartile contains firms with the highest allocations.

The results are presented in Table 6. It can be seen that firms in the first three quartiles demonstrate a significant positive correlation between the level of free-of-charge allowances and output, though this correlation weakens as the quartile increases. The respective output elasticities to the number of allowances are 0.156, 0.086 and 0.008 for the first, second and third quartiles. This relationship is no longer significant for firms in the fourth quartile. Therefore, our results indicate that the impact of the initial distribution of allowances on production levels is greater for firms receiving the fewest quotas. Firms in the first quartile are more responsive to the initial allocation than the full sample (see column 2, row 1, of Our results remain robust when fixed effects are introduced. Whatever the specification, we obtain a positive coefficient for our variable of interest. Firms' output levels increase with free-of-charge allowances under the ETS. More precisely, a 1% increase in free-of-charge allowances leads to an increase in output of between 0.011% and 0.014%.

Table 5, reported in the last column of Table 6). Neutrality between output levels and free-of-charge distribution is observed only for firms receiving the most quotas.

This result suggests that most firms do not perform the static trade-off identified by Montgomery (1972). When deciding on the level of emission reduction, they do not trade off the marginal cost of reducing emissions against the price of the allowance. One might think that the initial endowment would only be considered in the economic calculation when the free-of-charge quota is binding on firms, i.e. when they are in a position to purchase. To test this hypothesis, we introduce firms' emissions into our analysis to determine whether they have the required allowances for their production activity.

Therefore, we calculate the allowance "surplus" as the difference between the number of free allowances and the verified emissions at the end of the year, on the assumption that firms comply. Firms that have received more allowances than their verified emissions have a "surplus" of allowances, while the opposite is true in the case of a deficit. Although a shortage of allowances is considered to be indicative of buying behaviour, firms can bank their surplus. They are not necessarily in a selling position.

According to our argument, firms with an allowance surplus would be less likely to consider the level of their free-of-charge allowances when making production decisions. We test this assumption in Table 7. The first two columns show that firms with excess allowances are not

impacted by initial allowances in terms of production. The final columns consider firms with a deficit. Here, a 1% increase in free-of-charge allowances leads to an output increase of between 0.053% and 0.063%. Therefore, we can deduce that the initial distribution of allowances impacts firms' production decisions when they receive fewer allowances than they require. Firms do not consider the opportunity cost of the quota when making decisions. Firms purchase allowances for compliance purposes, which explains the positive correlation with production levels. In this case, carbon regulation may not be implemented at the lowest cost.

This econometric result corroborates the findings of Venmans (2016). Based on interviews with firm managers, the author concludes that free-of-charge allowances lower than emissions induce a stronger incentive to invest in abatement technologies than higher-than-emissions distributions. Firm managers attribute this discrepancy to the "endowment effect" of free allocation. Firms perceive the value of allowances they hold to be higher than the money they would obtain from selling them. This work is consistent with analyses by DellaVigna (2009) and Plott and Zeiler (2005), who sought to understand why behaviour diverges from that predicted by rational choice models. Venmans notes that this endowment effect leads to the ETS being perceived as more of a command-and-control approach than a market instrument. Our study corroborates this claim. Substituting auctioning for free-of-charge allowances is likely to result in increased investment in abatement.

Table 6. Effect of free-of-charge allowances on production levels by allowances quartile
 Dependent variable: $\ln Production$

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Full sample
$\ln FreeAllowances$	0.156***	0.086***	0.008**	0.017	0.011**
	(0.062)	(0.031)	(0.005)	(0.023)	(0.006)
$\ln Wages$	0.414***	0.188***	0.589***	0.099	0.440***
	(0.052)	(0.061)	(0.207)	(0.165)	(0.048)
$\ln Wages^2$	0.001	-0.075***	-0.139*	0.339**	-0.008
	(0.004)	(0.028)	(0.083)	(0.153)	(0.010)
$\ln Assets$	2.086**	-0.507	0.931	0.397	-0.058
	(0.839)	(0.614)	(0.813)	(0.472)	(0.175)
$\ln Assets^2$	0.014	-0.076***	-0.082	0.189*	0.029**
	(0.009)	(0.027)	(0.066)	(0.111)	(0.012)
$\ln Wages \times \ln Assets$	-0.004*	0.020***	0.018	-0.039*	-0.004
	(0.002)	(0.006)	(0.015)	(0.022)	(0.003)
Observations	678	816	856	861	3212
Firm fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Control variables	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Robust standard errors are in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Control variables: *Net fixed assets* and *Net tangible assets*

Table 7. Free-of-charge allowances effect as a function of the *Allocations – Emissions* difference
 Dependent variable *ln Production*

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	Excess	Excess	Excess	Deficit	Deficit	Deficit
<i>ln Free Allowances</i>	0.008	0.006	0.005	0.053***	0.063***	0.066***
	(0.006)	(0.006)	(0.006)	(0.017)	(0.018)	(0.018)
<i>ln Wages</i>	0.422***	0.425***	0.430***	0.557***	0.548***	0.523***
	(0.056)	(0.056)	(0.056)	(0.165)	(0.166)	(0.166)
<i>ln Wages</i> ²	-0.010	-0.010	-0.011	0.133	0.126	0.132
	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.010)	(0.082)	(0.082)	(0.082)
<i>ln Assets</i>	0.020	0.019	0.036	-1.697	-1.601	-1.735
	(0.190)	(0.190)	(0.190)	(1.190)	(1.189)	(1.190)
<i>ln Assets</i> ²	0.028**	0.028**	0.028**	0.149**	0.147**	0.149**
	(0.013)	(0.013)	(0.013)	(0.070)	(0.070)	(0.070)
<i>ln Wages × ln Assets</i>	-0.004	-0.004	-0.004	-0.032**	-0.031*	-0.032**
	(0.003)	(0.003)	(0.003)	(0.016)	(0.016)	(0.016)
Observations	2483	2483	2483	729	729	729
Firm fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year fixed effects	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO
Sector fixed effects	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
Phase fixed effects	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES
Control variables	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Robust standard errors are in parentheses. * p < 0.10, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01.

Control variables: Net fixed assets and Net tangible assets. "Excess": *Allocations – Emissions* > 0 and "Deficit": *Allocations – Emissions* < 0.

6.2 The different phases of the ETS

The EU ETS has undergone four distinct phases. The differences between these phases depend on the sectors covered, the pollution cap, the initial distribution of allowances and how new entrants are treated. According to our results, firms' production levels are affected by the initial distribution of allowances. This study aims to test whether this effect prevails in all phases. We conducted the test on Phases 2 and 3, which provided the greatest number of observations in our sample, and reported the results.

The first two columns of the table examine how the initial distribution of quotas affects production levels in Phases 2 and 3, respectively. In each case, firm- or sector-fixed effects are introduced. Regardless of the specified model, the effect of the initial distribution of allowances on the production level is not significant in Phase 2. By contrast, we do observe an

effect in Phase 3. A 1% reduction in free-of-charge allowances leads to a reduction in production of between 0.022% and 0.024%. As we have seen, free-of-charge allowances were more generous in Phase 2 than in Phase 3. Our results suggest that the initial distribution was binding in Phase 3 but not in Phase 2. This corroborates previous results, which considered the quantity of free-of-charge allowances and the surplus or deficit status of allowances. When free-of-charge allowances are reduced, firms must buy allowances to comply. In doing so, they do not consider the opportunity cost of the quota, nor do they appear to perform the static trade-off.

Table 8. Effect of free-of-charge allowances by phase
Dependent variable $\ln Production$

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	P2	P2	P3	P3
$\ln FreeAllowances$	-0.023	0.013	0.024*	0.022**
	(0.016)	(0.009)	(0.014)	(0.010)
$\ln Wages$	0.496***	0.625***	0.597***	0.851***
	(0.087)	(0.057)	(0.092)	(0.054)
$\ln Wages^2$	-0.114***	-0.093***	-0.051	-0.009
	(0.042)	(0.024)	(0.054)	(0.014)
$\ln Assets$	-4.088***	-0.793**	0.689**	1.501***
	(0.538)	(0.327)	(0.319)	(0.214)
$\ln Assets^2$	-0.065	-0.046*	0.044	0.084***
	(0.040)	(0.026)	(0.045)	(0.018)
$\ln Wages \times \ln Assets$	0.021**	0.013**	-0.009	-0.020***
	(0.009)	(0.006)	(0.009)	(0.004)
Observations	1325	1325	1620	1620
Firm fixed effects	YES	NO	YES	NO
Year fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES
Sector fixed effects	NO	YES	NO	YES
Control variables	YES	YES	YES	YES

Robust standard errors are in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Control variables: *Net fixed assets* and *Net tangible assets*.

6.3 Domestic or international market

Our sample comprises 165 firms operating in the domestic market and 211 firms operating in the international market. The European Union has implemented specific mechanisms to mitigate the risk of carbon leakage, such as allocating free allowances to so-called "exposed" sectors. If exporting firms receive more allowances than domestic firms, this corroborates

previous findings. Firms buy allowances when they need them. They do this to produce without making economic trade-offs. Those who receive the fewest quotas are the most constrained.

Table 9 illustrates the correlation between production levels and free-of-charge allowances for both groups. The first three columns consider firms operating internationally, while the last three consider those operating domestically.

Our results show that the initial allocation of allowances has no effect on firms operating in an international market. In contrast, the effect is positive and significant for domestic firms. A 1% increase in free allowances leads to a 0.024–0.030% increase in production.

The European Union has implemented specific mechanisms to mitigate the risk of carbon leakage, such as allocating free allowances to so-called "exposed" sectors. If exporting firms receive more allowances than domestic firms, this corroborates previous findings. Firms buy

allowances when they need them. They do this to produce without making economic trade-offs. Those who receive the fewest quotas are the most constrained.

Table 9. Effects of free-of-charge allowances by export status

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	International	International	International	Domestic	Domestic	Domestic
<i>ln FreeAllowances</i>	0.009	0.004	0.005	0.024***	0.030***	0.030***
	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.007)	(0.009)	(0.010)	(0.010)
<i>ln Wages</i>	0.381***	0.396***	0.400***	0.393***	0.385***	0.391***
	(0.071)	(0.072)	(0.072)	(0.077)	(0.077)	(0.077)
<i>ln Wages</i> ²	-0.048	-0.037	-0.042	0.004	0.004	0.004
	(0.037)	(0.037)	(0.037)	(0.011)	(0.011)	(0.011)
<i>ln Assets</i>	-0.319	-0.257	-0.285	0.228	0.228	0.232
	(0.241)	(0.242)	(0.241)	(0.291)	(0.291)	(0.290)
<i>ln Assets</i> ²	-0.031	-0.023	-0.026	0.052***	0.049***	0.052***
	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.028)	(0.016)	(0.016)	(0.016)
<i>ln Wages</i> × <i>ln Assets</i>	0.009	0.008	0.008	-0.010***	-0.010***	-0.010***
	(0.006)	(0.006)	(0.006)	(0.004)	(0.004)	(0.004)
Observations	1960	1960	1960	1252	1252	1252
Firm fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year fixed effects	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO
Sector fixed effects	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
Phase fixed effects	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES
Control variables	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Robust standard errors are in parentheses. * p < 0.10, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01.

Control variables: *Net fixed assets* and *Net tangible assets*

6.4 Production sectors

The firms in our sample belong to a variety of sectors. This diversity of activities is also a source of heterogeneity, given that each sector will have a different production structure. Our investigation, therefore, seeks to establish whether the impact of the initial distribution of allowances on production levels differs between sectors.

For the remainder of our study, we retained the six sectors containing more than 15 firms: the food industry (NAF 10); the paper and cardboard industry (NAF 17); the chemical industry (NAF 20); the manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products (NAF 23); the metallurgical industry (NAF 23); and the automotive industry (NAF 29).

The results are shown in Table 10. It turns out that the effect of free allowances also differs according to economic sector. In the food, minerals and metallurgy industries, the impact of distributing the allowances on firm output is positive and significant, with respective elasticities of 0.018, 0.031 and 0.024%. The marginal effects are particularly high for the minerals sector. However, they are not significant for the other sectors. Further analysis would consider initial allowance distribution by sector and compare them with firm needs.

Table 10. Effects of free-of-charge allowances by economic sectors

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	
	Food	Paper	Chemicals	Minerals	Metallurgy	Automotive	Full sample
$\ln FreeAllowances$	0.018***	0.018	-0.001	0.031***	0.024***	0.020	0.011**
	(0.005)	(0.012)	(0.013)	(0.007)	(0.006)	(0.024)	(0.006)
$\ln Wages$	0.229***	0.501***	0.247*	0.510***	0.817**	1.522***	0.440***
	(0.057)	(0.075)	(0.106)	(0.056)	(0.283)	(0.306)	(0.048)
$\ln Wages^2$	0.017	-0.176***	0.121	0.007	-0.065	-0.861**	-0.008
	(0.028)	(0.037)	(0.078)	(0.004)	(0.162)	(0.248)	(0.010)
$\ln Assets$	0.737	1.704*	-0.382	1.109***	1.463	-1.243	-0.058
	(0.420)	(0.739)	(0.634)	(0.271)	(1.079)	(0.645)	(0.175)
$\ln Assets^2$	-0.039*	-0.107**	0.132	0.029*	0.028	-0.525*	0.029**
	(0.018)	(0.034)	(0.079)	(0.014)	(0.109)	(0.213)	(0.012)
$\ln Wages \times \ln Assets$	0.009*	0.025**	-0.023	-0.008**	-0.007	0.104*	-0.004
	(0.004)	(0.008)	(0.017)	(0.003)	(0.024)	(0.040)	(0.003)
Observations	664	553	508	655	251	72	3212
Firm fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Year fixed effects	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Sector fixed effects	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO
Control variables	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Robust standard errors are in parentheses. * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Control variables: *Net fixed assets* and *Net tangible assets*.

7 Conclusion

When the initial distribution of allowances is exogenous and markets are competitive, as shown by Montgomery (1972), the initial distribution has no impact on the final distribution of allowances. This seminal theoretical result justifies the use of a tradable quota market instead of a Pigouvian tax. This approach gives the regulator greater flexibility in implementing environmental policy. In theory, this result can be easily transposed to the link between the initial distribution of quotas and production levels.

The aim of this study was to analyse the nature of this link for firms subject to the ETS. Our sample covers French manufacturing firms that mainly receive free allowances. To achieve

this, we employed a Translog production function and a panel data estimator from 2007 to 2018. Overall, we demonstrate that production levels increase with free-of-charge allowances. Therefore, this study challenges Montgomery's result.

Our results are particularly significant for firms in our sample that received the fewest free allowances. It suggests that firms do not engage in static trade-offs when deciding how many allowances to hold, viewing them instead as a right to produce. Firms purchase allowances to comply with environmental regulations without considering the trade-off between the allowance price and the marginal cost of reducing emissions. To test this idea, we divided our sample into those with an excess and those with a shortage of allowances to their compliance needs. Only firms that purchase allowances demonstrate a positive and significant correlation between the initial distribution and production levels, thus supporting the non-arbitrage hypothesis. The answer to our research question also depends on the phase of the ETS. The results are significant for the third phase, but not for the second. This could be explained by environmental policy becoming more stringent from the third phase onwards. We also demonstrate that free-of-charge allowances affect the production levels of firms operating primarily in the domestic market. The ETS implements specific mechanisms to prevent carbon leakage, meaning exporting firms are more likely to receive more allowances than firms operating on the domestic market. This corroborates the previous results. Finally, the main result appears to hold for the food, minerals and metallurgy sectors, but not for the paper, chemicals and automotive sectors.

Despite the initial distribution of allowances being exogenous and the allowance market not exhibiting market imperfections, the initial allocation still impacts the production level. Therefore, Montgomery's result is challenged in the EU ETS over the period considered. Our results suggest that firms exhibit myopic behaviour, failing to recognise the static trade-off between the price of allowances and the marginal cost of emission reductions. Emission reductions would not be achieved at the lowest cost on the EU ETS. This study, therefore, contributes to existing research on the divergence between observed behaviour and that predicted by rational choice models. The EU ETS is seen as more of a command-and-control policy than a market instrument.

Further development of our analysis is required, including a more detailed examination of the cost-efficiency criteria in the EU ETS. The widespread use of auctions could affect our results. Additionally, more sector-specific analyses should be conducted to better understand the differences in firms' behaviour across different sectors. Finally, a larger sample of firms would help investigate the impact of free-of-charge allowances on firms' production levels, particularly for those receiving the most (or least) allowances in a given sector, or operating on a domestic or international market. The analysis could also be conducted by considering firms in exposed and non-exposed sectors separately.

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9 Appendix

9.1 Sectors full names

Table A- 1. NAF (French classification of activities) and variables' names

NAF	Official names	Variable names
10	Manufacture of food products	Food
11	Manufacture of beverages	Beverages
12	Manufacture of tobacco products	Tobacco products
13	Manufacture of textiles	Textiles
16	Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of articles of straw and plaiting materials	Wood and cork products
17	Manufacture of paper and paper products	Paper
19	Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products	Coking and refining
20	Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products	Chemicals
21	Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations	Pharmaceutical industry
22	Manufacture of rubber and plastic products	Rubber and plastic
23	Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products	Minerals
24	Manufacture of basic metals	Basic metals
25	Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment	Fabricated metal products
26	Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products	Computer electronic optical
27	Manufacture of electrical equipment	Electrical equipment
28	Manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c.	Machinery
29	Manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	Automotive
30	Manufacture of other transport equipment	Other transport equipment
31	Manufacture of furniture	Furniture

n.e.c: not elsewhere classified

9.2 Firms with capacity extensions

Table A- 2. List of firms with capacity extensions

ARKEMA FRANCE
SOLVAY OPERATIONS FRANCE
SICAL
SGD S A
LUCART SAS
MAXAM TAN SAS
NIPRO PHARMAPACKAGING FRANCE
TEREOS STARCH & SWEETENERS EUROPE
COOPERATIVE ISIGNY-SAINTE MERE
KNAUF INSULATION LANNEMEZAN
LHOIST FRANCE OUEST
RHODIA OPERATIONS
INGREDIA
SOLEVAL FRANCE
ADISSEO FRANCE SAS
NOVAPEX